

Preliminary English translation
of Pseudo-Athanasius's *Quaestiones aliae* (*Ἐτεραί τινες ἐρωτήσεις*)¹

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Ἐρώτησις α'. Τί ἐστι Θεός; (27)

Ἀπόκρισις. Θεός ἐστιν οὐσία νοερὰ, ἀθεώρητος τε καὶ ἀνερμήνευτος. Θεός ἐστι πνεῦμα ἄϋλον, ὀφθαλμὸς ἀκοίμητος, καὶ νοῦς ἀκίνητος. Θεός ἐστιν (30) οὐσία δημιουργικὴ πάντων τῶν ἀοράτων καὶ ὀρωμένων κτισμάτων.

Ἐρώτ. β'. Καὶ διὰ τί λέγεται Θεός, ὁ Θεός; (34)

Ἀπόκ. Θεός λέγεται ἀπὸ τοῦ θεωρεῖν τὰ πάντα, (35) οἶονεὶ θεωρὸς, καὶ Θεός, ἦγουν θεατῆς πάντων. Καὶ πάλιν Θεός λέγεται ἀπὸ τοῦ θέειν καὶ τρέχειν (38) νοητῶς ἀχρόνως τὰ πάντα. Ὁ γὰρ Θεός ἀεὶ πανταχοῦ πάρεστιν. (40)

Ἐρώτ. γ'. Καὶ πόσοι θεοὶ εἰσιν;

Ἀπόκ. Εἷς Θεός τῶν θεῶν, καὶ Κύριος τῶν κυριευόντων, καὶ πλὴν αὐτοῦ οὐκ ἔστιν ἄλλος. Λέγονται δὲ θεοὶ καὶ οἱ ἄνθρωποι κατὰ χάριν· ὡς τό· «Ἐγὼ εἶπα, Θεοὶ ἐστε, καὶ υἱοὶ Ὑψίστου πάντες.»

Ἐρώτ. δ'. Καὶ ὡς ἔνι εἷς, πῶς λέγομεν αὐτὸν τὸν ἕνα Θεὸν τρισυπόστατον, Πατέρα, καὶ Υἱὸν, καὶ ἅγιον Πνεῦμα; Ἴδου γὰρ τρεῖς λέγομεν, καὶ οὐχ ἕνα. Ἀλλὰ δίδαξον ἡμῖν πῶς ἐστιν εἷς Θεός· καὶ πῶς πάλιν τρία πρόσωπα περὶ Θεοῦ λέγομεν. Θαυμαστὸν ἡμῖν δοκεῖ τοῦτο, ὅπως καὶ εἷς ἐστιν ὁ Θεός, καὶ τρία τὰ πρόσωπα αὐτοῦ.

Ἀπόκ. Ἄκουε συνετῶς, καὶ νοήσεις τὸ τῆς ἁγίας Τριάδος μυστήριον, καθὼς δύναται νοῦς ἀνθρώπων νοῆσαι. Ὡς ἐμοὶ πλὴν

Question 1: What is God?

Answer: God is essence spiritual [lit. intellectual], invisible and unintelligible. God is an immaterial spirit, an unresting eye, an immovable mind. God is essence creative of all invisible and visible creatures.

Question 2: And why is called *θεός* “God” the God?

Answer: He is called *θεός* from *θεωρεῖν* “spectating” everything, as if he was a spectator, and *θεός* “God” that is spectator of all things. And again, he is called *θεός* “God” from *θέειν* and *τρέχειν* “running” spiritually [lit. intellectually] non-temporally all things. For God is ever present everywhere.

Question 3: And how many gods are existing?

Answer: There is one God of gods and Lord of all lords [lit. Dominator of all who are dominating] and no one is existing but Him. Humans are also called *θεοὶ* “gods”; as in verse: “I said, ‘Gods you are, and all of you are sons of the Most High.’”

Question 4: And while he is one, how do we call this one God trihypostatic (i.e. three-hypostases) Father and Son and holy Spirit? Look, we talk about three and not about one. But teach us how is it that God is one; and how we talk for God three persons. I believe that this is marvelous, that

¹ *Patrologia Graeca* 28:773-796 {2035.081}.

δοκεῖ, πρὸς τὴν κατὰ δύναμιν ἡμῖν τῶν λέξεων λέγεται τοῦτο. Ὁ γὰρ Θεὸς ἀνερμήνευτός ἐστι, καὶ διὰ τοῦτο οὐ δυνάμεθα καταλαβεῖν αὐτοῦ τὴν φύσιν· οὐδὲ ὅμοιος ἡμῶν ἐστι μονοπρόσωπος. Εἰ γὰρ ἦν μονοπρόσωπος, ἐγινώσκομεν ἄν αὐτὸν, ὡς ἐγινώσκομεν ἀλλήλους ἡμᾶς. Ἄλλ' ἔστιν εἷς μὲν ὁ Θεός, τὰ δὲ πρόσωπα αὐτοῦ τρία. Καὶ βλέπε ἀπάρτι τὰ λεγόμενα. Ὡσπερ ἥλιος ἓν εἷς, ὁ δὲ ἥλιος ἔχει ἀκτῖνα καὶ φῶς, καὶ εἰσὶν ἐν τῷ ἡλίῳ τρία πρόσωπα, δίσκος, ἀκτίς, καὶ φῶς· καὶ δίσκος μὲν καυχίον τοῦ ἡλίου, ἀκτίς δὲ καταβαιομένη λαμπαδοφανῶς καὶ κρούουσα πρὸς τὴν γῆν· φῶς δὲ τὸ φωτίζον,

καὶ εἰς τοὺς ἐπισκιώδεις τόπους χωρὶς ἀκτῖνος. Καὶ ἰδοὺ πρόσωπα μὲν τρία, δίσκος, ἀκτίς, καὶ φῶς. Οὐ λέγομεν δὲ τρεῖς ἡλίους, ἀλλ' ἓνα ἥλιον, οὐδὲ λέγομεν πρόσωπον ἓν, ἀλλὰ πρόσωπα τρία. Ἐὰν γὰρ ἐρωτηθῆς, ὅτι πόσοι ἥλιοι ἐν τῷ οὐρανῷ, μέλλεις εἰπεῖν, ὅτι ἥλιος εἷς ἐστίν· εἰ δ' ἐρωτηθῆς, ὅτι πρόσωπα τοῦ ἡλίου πόσα ἐστὶ, μέλλεις εἰπεῖν, ὅτι τρία, δίσκος, ἀκτίς, καὶ φῶς· οὕτω νόει καὶ περὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ. Θεὸς μὲν εἷς, πρόσωπα δὲ τοῦ ἐνὸς Θεοῦ τρία, Πατὴρ, Υἱοῦ, καὶ ἁγίου Πνεύματος. Καὶ ἐκ τούτου γίνωσκε, ὅτι, ὡσπερ ὁ ἥλιός ἐστι τριπρόσωπος, οὕτω καὶ εἷς Θεὸς τρισυπόστατος. Τύπος γὰρ τοῦ Πατρὸς ἐστὶν ὁ δίσκος ὁ ἡλιακός, τύπος τοῦ Υἱοῦ ἐστὶν ἡ ἀκτίς, τύπος τοῦ ἁγίου Πνεύματος ἐστὶ τὸ φῶς τοῦ ἡλίου. Καὶ εἰπέ οὕτως· Ἐπὶ τοῦ ἡλίου δίσκος, ἀκτίς, καὶ φῶς· οὐ λέγομεν δὲ τρεῖς ἡλίους, ἀλλ' ἓνα καὶ μόνον· ὁμοίως καὶ ἐπὶ Θεοῦ, Πατὴρ, Υἱός, καὶ ἅγιον Πνεῦμα εἷς Θεός, καὶ οὐ τρεῖς. Καὶ πάλιν εἰπέ οὕτως· Ἐπὶ τοῦ ἡλίου ἀχώριστος ὁ δίσκος, καὶ ἡ ἀκτίς, καὶ τὸ φῶς· οὐ γὰρ χωρίζονται ἀπ' ἀλλήλων, διὰ

God is both one and also three are his persons.

Answer: Listen intelligibly and you will understand the mystery of the holy Trinity, the way that is able to understand the human mind. But as for me I think that according to the power of the words are said these to us. Because God is inexplicable and for this reason, we are not able to understand his nature; neither he is single-person in similarity with us. If he were single-person, we would know him, as we know each other of us. But God is one, but his persons (lit. faces) are three. And, henceforth see what is said. Like as the sun is one, but the sun has rays (lit. a ray) and light, and there are in the sun three persons (lit. faces), disk, ray and light; the disk is the cup of the sun, the ray coming down with shining light and striking towards the earth; the light that is illuminating,

and in shadowy places without a ray. Thus, the persons (lit. faces) are three: the disk, the ray and the light. We don't call them three suns but one sun, neither we say one person (lit. face) but three persons. And if you are asked how many suns are at heaven, you will answer that the sun is one; and if you are asked how many the persons (lit. faces) of the sun are, you will answer that they are three: the disk, the ray and the light; in this way you should understand also about God. God is one but the persons (lit. faces) of the one God are three, Father's, Son's and holy Spirit's. And from this you should know that in the way that the sun is three-faced, the same also the one God is trihypostatic. A symbol (lit. type) for the Father is the solar disk, a symbol for the Son is the ray, a symbol for the holy Spirit is the light of the sun. And you should answer this way: On the sun there is the disk, the ray and the light; but we don't say that there are three suns but one and only one; similarly about God: the Father, the Son and the holy Spirit are one God and not

τοῦτο λέγεται καὶ εἷς Θεός, καὶ οὐ τρεῖς· διότι οὐ χωρίζονται τὰ τρία πρόσωπα, τοῦ τε Πατρὸς, καὶ τοῦ Υἱοῦ, καὶ τοῦ ἁγίου Πνεύματος, τοῦ ἐνὸς Θεοῦ ἀπ' ἀλλήλων. Καὶ ὡσπερ ὁ δίσκος ὁ ἡλιακὸς γεννᾷ τὴν ἀκτῖνα, καὶ ἐκπορεύει τὸ φῶς· οὕτω καὶ ὁ Θεὸς καὶ Πατὴρ γεννᾷ τὸν Υἱὸν καὶ ἐκπορεύει καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα ἅγιον. Βλέπε συνετῶς· Ὡσπερ ἡ ἀκτὶς τοῦ ἡλίου καταβαίνει ἐξ οὐρανοῦ πρὸς τὴν γῆν, καὶ οὔτε τοῦ ἡλιακοῦ δίσκου χωρίζεται, οὔτε ἐκ τοῦ οὐρανοῦ λείπει, οὔτε ἀπὸ τῆς γῆς, ἀλλ' ἔστι καὶ ἐν τῷ ἡλιακῷ δίσκῳ, καὶ ἐν τῷ οὐρανῷ, καὶ ἐν τῇ γῇ, καὶ πανταχοῦ, καὶ οὔτε τῶν ἄνω λείπει, οὔτε τῶν κάτω· οὕτω καὶ ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ κατήλθε πρὸς τὴν γῆν, καὶ οὔτε ἐκ τοῦ Πατρὸς ἔλειπε, οὔτε ἐκ τῶν οὐρανῶν, οὔτε ἐκ τῆς γῆς· ἀλλ' ἦν καὶ ἐν τοῖς κόλποις τοῦ Πατρὸς ἀχώριστος, καὶ ἄνω καὶ κάτω, καὶ πανταχοῦ· καὶ οὐδ' ἐκ τινος ἔλειπε. Καὶ ὡσπερ τὸ ἡλιακὸν φῶς ἔστι καὶ ἐν τῷ δίσκῳ τῷ ἡλιακῷ καὶ ἐν τῇ ἀκτίνι, καὶ ἐν τῷ οὐρανῷ, καὶ ἐν τῇ γῇ, καὶ εἰσέρχεται ἐν ταῖς οἰκίαις καὶ πανταχοῦ, καὶ φωτίζει· οὕτω καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον καὶ μετὰ τοῦ

three. And, again, you should answer this way: On the sun the disk, the ray and the light are inseparable; they are not separated from each other, and for this reason is said that God is one and not three; because they are not separated the three persons (lit. faces)—Father's, Son's and holy Spirit's—of the one God from each other. In the way that the solar disk begets the ray and sends out (or, proceeds) the light, the same also the God and Father begets the Sun and proceeds (or, sends out) the holy Spirit. And see intelligibly: in the way that sun's ray comes down from heaven on earth and neither is separated from the solar disk nor is missing from heaven and also from earth, but it is [in the same time] at the solar disk and at heaven and on earth and everywhere, and is not missing neither from the things above nor at the things below; the same also the Son and Word of God came down to earth, and he was not missing from the Father, neither from heaven nor from earth; but he was [in the same time] at Father's bosom unseparated, and up and down and everywhere; and he was not missing from anyone. And in the way the solar light is [in the same time] at the solar disk and at the ray and also at heaven and earth and gets into the houses and everywhere and illuminates; the same also for the holy Spirit that [in the same time] is with

Πατρός ἐστι, καὶ μετὰ τοῦ Υἱοῦ, καὶ ἄνω καὶ κάτω, καὶ πάντα ἄνθρωπον φωτίζει, καὶ οὐ λείπει ποτέ. «Τὸ γὰρ Πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον,» φησὶν ὁ ἀπόστολος Παῦλος, «πάντα ἐρευνᾷ, καὶ τὰ βάθη τοῦ Θεοῦ.» Ἴδου λοιπὸν, ὡσπερ δὲ οὐκ οἶδαμέν ποτε, οὐδὲ γινώσκειν δυνάμεθα, ποταπὸς ἦν ὅταν δὲ ἴδωμεν τὴν εἰκόνα αὐτοῦ, τότε μικρὸν κατανοοῦμεν τὸν χαρακτῆρα τοῦ προσώπου αὐτοῦ· οὕτω μοι νόει καὶ περὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ. «Τὸν γὰρ Θεὸν οὐδεὶς ἐώρακε πώποτε.» Πῶς οὖν αὐτὸν καταλαβέσθαι

the Father and with the Son and up and down, and illuminates every man and is never missing. “For the holy Spirit,” says apostle Paul, “searches everything, even the depths of God.” Look, now, that in the way we did not ever know Him neither we are capable of knowing Him, what kind He was; but when we saw his image, then we understand by little the character of his person (lit. face); this way I understand also about God. “But no one has ever seen God.” And how would it be possible for

τινὰ δύναται; ἀλλ' ἐπειδὴ φῶς ἐστι καὶ ὀνομάζεται ὁ Θεὸς, ἐκ τοῦ αἰσθητοῦ τούτου φωτὸς ἐξεικονίζομεν αὐτὸν, ὥστε λοιπὸν, ὡς προείπομεν, εἰς τύπον τοῦ ἡλίου χαρακτηρίζομεν τὴν ἁγίαν Τριάδα, λέγοντες εἶναι τὸν μὲν Πατέρα δίσκον, τὸν δὲ Υἱὸν ἀκτῖνα, τὸ δὲ Πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον φῶς ἐκ φωτός. Καὶ ὡσπερ ὁ δίσκος, καὶ ἡ ἀκτίς, καὶ τὸ φῶς ἓν εἰσι καὶ τρία, ἀμερίστως μεριζόμενα, οὕτω καὶ ὁ Θεὸς ἡ Τριάς, ὁ Πατήρ, καὶ ὁ Υἱὸς, καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον, ἓν ἐστι καὶ τρία, μεριζόμενα μὲν τοῖς προσώποις κατὰ τὸν ἡλίον, ἀμέριστα δὲ τῇ φύσει διαμένοντα. Καὶ ὡσπερ ὁ δίσκος τοῦ ἡλίου μόνος ἐστὶν αἷτιος καὶ ἀγέννητος, ἡ δὲ ἀκτίς αἰτιατὴ καὶ γενητὴ ἐκ τοῦ δίσκου, τὸ δὲ φῶς ἐκπορευτὸν ἐκ μόνου τοῦ δίσκου, διὰ τὸ τῆς ἀκτίνος πεμπόμενον, καὶ καταλάμπων τὰ περίγεια· οὕτω καὶ ὁ Θεὸς καὶ Πατήρ αὐτὸς μόνος ἐστὶν αἷτιος τοῖς δυοῖς καὶ ἀγέννητος· ὁ δὲ Υἱὸς ἐκ μόνου τοῦ Πατρὸς αἰτιατὸς καὶ γεννητὸς· καὶ αὐτὸ τὸ Πνεῦμα ἐκ μόνου τοῦ Πατρὸς αἰτιατὸν καὶ ἐκπορευτὸν, διὰ δὲ τοῦ Υἱοῦ ἐν τῷ κόσμῳ ἀποστελλόμενον. Καὶ οὕτως ἔχε, καὶ νόει, καὶ πίστευε περὶ Θεοῦ. Εἰ δ' οὐκ ἀρκεῖ σοι τὸ τοῦ ἡλίου παράδειγμα εἰς ἐπίγνωσιν τῆς τρισυποστάτου θεότητος, βλέπε καὶ ἄλλην εἰκόνα Θεοῦ· ἔστι δὲ ἡ ψυχὴ τοῦ ἀνθρώπου. Ὅτε γὰρ ἔμελλεν ὁ Θεὸς πλάσσειν τὸν ἄνθρωπον, εἶπε· «Ποιήσωμεν ἄνθρωπον κατ' εἰκόνα ἡμετέραν καὶ καθ' ὁμοίωσιν.» Ἴδου λοιπὸν, ὁ ἄνθρωπος εἰκὼν ἐστὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ, ἡ γοῦν ἡ ψυχὴ τοῦ ἀνθρώπου. Ἐνὶ δὲ ἡ ψυχὴ τοῦ ἀνθρώπου μία μὲν, τρισυπόστατος δέ· τρία πρόσωπα ἔχει ἡ ψυχὴ· καὶ πῶς; ἄκουσον. Ἔστιν ἡ ψυχὴ ἐν πρόσωπον· ἡ δὲ ψυχὴ γεννᾷ τὸν λόγον, καὶ ἰδοὺ ὁ λόγος ἄλλο πρόσωπον. Ἡ ψυχὴ ἐκπορεύει

someone to understand him? But because God is and named light, from the light that is perceived) by the senses we represent (or, symbolize him, so that, then, as we aforesaid, as a type (i.e. symbol that represents, that is typifying) of the sun we characterize the holy Trinity, by calling the Father disk, the Son ray, and the holy Spirit light from light. And in the way that the disk and the ray and the light are one and three, being inseparably separated, this way also God the Trinity, the Father, the Son and the holy Spirit, is one and three, separated on the one hand as regards the persons (lit. faces) in accordance with the sun, remaining unseparated as regards the nature. And in the way that the disk of the sun is the only cause and unoriginated, the ray is effect and originating from the disk, the light proceeding only from the disk, that is emitted (or, sent) through the ray and shinning the things around earth; this way also God and Father only he himself is the only cause for the two and unoriginated; the Son effected and originating only by the Father; and the Spirit itself effected and proceeding only from the Father, through the Son that is being sent to the world. This way you must know and understand and believe about God. And if it is not enough for you the example of the sun for getting knowledge of the trihypostatic Deity, see also the other similitude (lit. image) of God: it is the human soul. When God was going to create the man (i.e. human being), he said: "Let us make man in our image, after our likeness." Look, therefore, the man is image of God, that is the soul of the man. The soul that is in the man is one but trihypostatic; three persons (or, faces, or aspects) has the soul; and how is this so? Listen. The soul is one person; the soul begets the logos (i.e. reason; or, word) kai, look, the logos is another person. The soul proceeds (lit. sends out)

καὶ τὴν πνοὴν, καὶ ἰδοὺ ἡ πνοὴ ἄλλο πρόσωπον. Ἴδοὺ πρόσωπα τρία, ψυχὴ, λόγος, καὶ πνοή. Καὶ γὰρ ὁ λόγος καὶ ἡ πνοὴ τῆς ψυχῆς εἰσιν, οὐ τοῦ σώματος, ἐπειδὴ, τῆς ψυχῆς ἐξεληθείσης ἐκ τοῦ σώματος, οὔτε λόγος ἐναπομένει τῷ σώματι, οὔτε πνοή, ἀλλὰ κεῖται τὸ σῶμα καὶ ἄπνουν καὶ ἄλογον. Ὁ δὲ λόγος καὶ ἡ πνοὴ εἰσι μετὰ τῆς ψυχῆς· καὶ ἐκ τούτου δῆλόν ἐστιν, ὡς, ὅτι καὶ ὁ λόγος καὶ ἡ πνοὴ ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς εἰσι, καὶ τῆς ψυχῆς εἰσι πρόσωπα· καὶ ἰδοὺ λοιπὸν ἡ ψυχὴ πρόσωπον ἓν, καὶ ὁ λόγος ἄλλο πρόσωπον, καὶ ἡ πνοὴ ἕτερον πρόσωπον. Ἴδοὺ τρία πρόσωπα τῆς ψυχῆς, ἀλλὰ ψυχὴ μία, καὶ οὐ τρεῖς. Εἰ γὰρ ἐρωτηθῆς, πόσας ψυχὰς ἔχει ὁ ἄνθρωπος; μέλλεις εἰπεῖν, ὅτι μίαν. Ἐὰν δὲ ἐρωτηθῆς καὶ πόσα πρόσωπά εἰσι τῆς ψυχῆς; ἀρμόζει ἴν' εἴποις, ὅτι τρία· ἐπειδὴ ψυχὴ, λόγος καὶ πνοή, μία ψυχὴ, καὶ πρόσωπα τρία. Καὶ ἔστι μὲν ἡ ψυχὴ εἰς τύπον τοῦ Πατρὸς· ὁ δὲ λόγος τῆς ψυχῆς εἰς τύπον τοῦ Υἱοῦ καὶ Λόγου τοῦ Θεοῦ· ἡ δὲ πνοὴ τῆς ψυχῆς εἰς τύπον τοῦ ἁγίου Πνεύματος. Ὡς γὰρ ἡ ψυχὴ ἀγέννητος, οὕτω καὶ ὁ Θεὸς καὶ Πατὴρ ἀγέννητος· καὶ ὡσπερ ὁ λόγος γεννητὸς ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς, οὕτω καὶ ὁ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ γεννητὸς ἀπὸ τοῦ Πατρὸς· καὶ καθάπερ ἡ πνοὴ ἐκπορευτὴ ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς, οὕτω καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον ἐκπορευτὸν ἀπὸ τοῦ Πατρὸς. Καὶ εἶπον οὕτω· Ψυχὴ, λόγος καὶ πνοή, μία ψυχὴ, καὶ οὐ τρεῖς· ἀχώριστος γὰρ ὁ λόγος καὶ ἡ πνοὴ ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς. Ὁμοίως Πατὴρ, καὶ Υἱὸς, ἦτοι Λόγος, καὶ Πνεῦμα, εἷς Θεός, καὶ οὐ τρεῖς· ἀχώριστος γὰρ (15) ὁ Λόγος καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα τὸ θεῖον ἐκ τοῦ Πατρὸς. Καὶ καθάπερ ἀόρατος ἡ ψυχὴ, οὕτως ἀόρατος καὶ ὁ Θεός. Καὶ οὕτως ὅταν διαστάσεις ἐν τῷ νοῖ σου, καὶ λέγεις, πῶς ἔνι ὁ Θεός εἷς, καὶ ἔνι καὶ τρισυπόστατος; ἐνθυμοῦ τῆς ψυχῆς σου, καὶ λέγε· Ὡσπερ ἡ ψυχὴ μου (20) μία ἐστίν, ἀλλὰ καὶ τρισυπόστατος, ψυχὴ, λόγος, καὶ πνοή· οὕτω καὶ ὁ Θεός εἷς ἐστίν, ἀλλ' ἔστι καὶ

also the breath, and, look, the breath is another person. Look the three persons: soul, logos and breath. And the logos and the breath of the soul do not belong to the body, because when the soul comes out of the body, neither logos remains in the body, neither breath, but the body is laid both breathless and alogos (i.e. without reasoning ability). And logos and breath are together with (or, belong to) the soul; and from this it is evident that both logos and breath are from the soul, and they are persons of the soul; and, look, the soul is one person and logos is another person and the breath is a different person. Look, three persons of the soul but the soul is one and not three. And if you may be asked 'how many souls has the man?' you will answer 'one.' And if you may be asked 'and how many persons are of the soul?' it is proper to answer 'three.' Because soul, logos and breath are one soul and three persons. And the soul can be taken as a figure (or, symbol) of the Father; the logos of the soul as a figure of the Son and Logos of God; and the breath of soul as a figure of the holy Spirit. And just as soul is unbegotten, the same way the God and Father is unbegotten; and just as logos is born from the soul, the same way the Word of God was begotten by the Father; and just as the breath is proceeding from soul, the same way the holy Spirit is proceeding from the Father. And say this: Soul, logos and breath are one soul and not three; unseparated from the soul is logos and breath. Similarly the Father, and Son—that is, Logos—and Spirit are one God and not three; unseparated is the Logos and the divine Spirit from the Father. And just as the soul is invisible, the same way is also God invisible. And you when you doubt in your mind this way by saying 'how is God one and is he is also trihypostatic?' you should remember your soul and say: "Just as my soul is one but also trihypostatic—

τρισυπόστατος, Πατήρ, Λόγος, και Πνεῦμα ἅγιον. Καὶ λέγε ἐν τῷ νοῖ σου, ὅτι, ἐὰν ἡ ψυχὴ, τὸ ποίημα τοῦ Θεοῦ, ὁμοίως καὶ ὁ ἥλιος, ἐστὶ τρισυπόστατος, ἡ δὲ (25) φύσις αὐτῶν μία· πόσω μᾶλλον ὁ Θεὸς ὁ ποιητὴς

τούτων! Οὐκ ἐνδέχεται τὸ εἶναι οὕτως, ὥστε εἶναι αὐτὸν ἓνα τῆ φύσει, καὶ τρισυπόστατον τοῖς προσώποις; καὶ ἀληθῶς ἐνδέχεται. Ὡς γὰρ ψυχὴ, λόγος καὶ πνοὴ τρία πρόσωπα, καὶ μία φύσις ψυχῆς, καὶ (30) οὐ τρεῖς ψυχαί· οὕτω Πατήρ, Λόγος καὶ Πνεῦμα ἅγιον, τρία πρόσωπα, καὶ εἷς τῆ φύσει Θεὸς, καὶ οὐ τρεῖς θεοί. Οὕτως ἐὰν συλλογίζῃ πάντοτε, οὐ μὴ βλασφημῆσῃ ἐπὶ τῆς ἁγίας Τριάδος.

Ἀλλὰ ἀκμὴν καὶ ἄλλην εἰκόνα Θεοῦ ἄκουσον, ἀγαπητέ. Ἴδου τὸ πῦρ ἓν ἐστὶ, ἄλλως καὶ τρισυπόστατον. Αὐτὸ γὰρ ἓν ἐστὶ τὸ ὑποκείμενον πῦρ, τὸ δὲ καυστικὸν αὐτοῦ ἕτερον πρόσωπον, καὶ τὸ φωτιστικὸν αὐτοῦ ἄλλο πρόσωπον. Ἴδου λοιπὸν τρία πρόσωπα τοῦ ἑνὸς πυρὸς, ἡγουν τὸ ὑποκείμενον πῦρ, (40) καὶ τὸ καυστικὸν, καὶ τὸ φωτιστικόν· μία δὲ φύσις τοῦ πυρὸς, καὶ οὐ τρεῖς. Ὅμοίως καὶ ἐπὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ· ὁ γὰρ Πατήρ ἓν τὸ πῦρ, ὁ Υἱὸς τὸ καυστικόν, καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον ἓν τὸ φωτιστικόν. Καὶ ὡσπερ ἐπὶ τοῦ πυρὸς, τὸ πῦρ, τὸ καυστικόν, καὶ τὸ φωτιστικόν, (45) καὶ αὐτὸ τὸ ὑποκείμενον πῦρ, ἓν λέγομεν, καὶ οὐ τρία· οὕτω λέγομεν καὶ ἐπὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ τὰ τρία πρόσωπα, τὸν τε Πατέρα, καὶ Υἱὸν, καὶ τὸ ἅγιον Πνεῦμα, Θεὸν ἓνα λέγομεν, καὶ οὐ τρεῖς. Καὶ περὶ μὲν τῆς ἐπιγνώσεως τῆς ἁγίας Τριάδος ἀρκεῖτω ταῦτα τῷ (50) πιστεύοντι.

Πλὴν ἄκουσον καὶ ἄλλο πρὸς τούτοις μυστήριον. Ὁ λόγος τοῦ ἀνθρώπου διπλὴν ἔχει τὴν γέννησιν, καὶ ἐν δυοῖς φοραῖς γεννᾶται· μίαν μὲν φορὰν γεννᾶται ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς, ἑτέραν δὲ ἀπὸ τῶν χειλέων. Καὶ

soul, logos and breath; so also God is one but is also trihypostatic—Father, Logos, and holy Spirit.” And say in your mind that “if the soul, the creature of God, and similarly the sun, is trihypostatic and their nature is one, how much more God, the creator

of them?” Isn’t to be admitted that it is so, so that he is one as regards his nature and trihypostatic as regards his persons? And it is truly admitted so. Just as the soul, logos and breath are three persons and the nature of the soul is one and not three souls; the same way Father, Logos and holy Spirit are three persons, but one God as regards the nature, not three gods. If you always think this way, you will never blaspheme about the holy Trinity.

But, dear, hear that there is yet another image of God. Look, the fire is one, but otherwise is also trihypostatic. The underlying fire is one, and its burning capability is another person and its illuminating capability is a different person. Look, then, there are three persons of the one fire, that is the underlying fire, and the burning capability and the illuminating capability; the nature of the fire is one and not three. Similarly also about God; the Father is the fire, the Son is the burning capability and the holy Spirit is the illuminating capability. And just as about fire, the fire, the burning capability and the illuminating capability and the underlying fire itself we say that it is one and not three; the same way we talk about the three persons of God, the Father, and the Son, and the holy Spirit, we say [that they are] one God and not three. And about the knowledge of the holy Spirit let these be sufficient for the believer.

But hear another mystery in relation with them. The logos (i.e. both reason and word)

γεννᾶται (55) μὲν ὁ λόγος τοῦ ἀνθρώπου ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς, ὅταν ἐνθυμηθῆ τις εἰπεῖν τι. Ἡ γὰρ ἐνθύμησις πρώτη γέννησις λέγεται τοῦ λόγου, ἐπεὶ ἐνθυμεῖται τοῦ εἰπεῖν ἐκεῖνον τὸν λόγον· οὐ λέγει δὲ τοῦτον διὰ τῶν χειλέων, @1 (781) ἀλλὰ φυλάττει τὸν λόγον ἢ ψυχὴ ἐν τοῖς κόλποις αὐτῆς· καὶ ἔστιν ἡ ἐνθύμησις ἐκεῖνη πρώτη γέννησις τοῦ λόγου ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς. Ὅμως, κἄν γεννηθῆ ὁ λόγος ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς, πρώτην γέννησιν ὅταν ἐνθυμηθῆ αὐτὸν ἢ ψυχὴ, ἀλλ' οὐ φανεροῖ αὐτὸν, ἀκμὴν (5) δὲ φυλάττει αὐτόν. Ὅταν δὲ θελήσῃ τοῦ φανερωῶσαι τὸν λόγον, τότε γεννᾷ αὐτόν ἐκ τῶν χειλέων. Αὐτὴ

τὸν λόγον, τότε γεννᾷ αὐτόν ἐκ τῶν χειλέων. Αὐτὴ δὲ ἢ ἐκ τῶν χειλέων δευτέρα γέννησις τοῦ λόγου, αὐτὴ φανεροῖ τὸν λόγον ἐν τοῖς πᾶσι, καὶ οὐκ ἔτι λοιπὸν ὁ λόγος ἀφανὴς λέγεται, ἀλλ' ἐμφανής. Ὅταν (10) δὲ γεννηθῆ ὁ λόγος διὰ τῶν χειλέων, τότε οἱ πάντες ἀκούουσιν αὐτόν, καὶ φανερός γίνεται τοῖς πᾶσι· καὶ λέγεται αὕτη ἡ γέννησις ἢ διὰ τῶν χειλέων δευτέρα γέννησις τοῦ λόγου· ὥστε δύο εἰσὶν αἱ γεννήσεις τοῦ λόγου ἡμῶν· μία μὲν ἐκ τῆς ψυχῆς, ὅταν ἐνθυμηθῆ (15) τοῦ λαλῆσαι τὸν λόγον, ἥτις καὶ πρώτη γέννησις λέγεται· καὶ ἕτερα ἐκ τῶν χειλέων, ἥτις φανεροῖ τὸν λόγον πᾶσιν ἀνθρώποις, ἥτις καὶ δευτέρα γέννησις λέγεται. Μάνθανε οὖν ἀκριβῶς, ὅτι, ὡσπερ ὁ λόγος τοῦ ἀνθρώπου δύο γεννήσεις ἔχει, μίαν ἐκ τῆς ψυχῆς, (20) καὶ ἄλλην ἐκ τῶν χειλέων, οὕτως καὶ ὁ τοῦ Θεοῦ Λόγος δύο γεννήσεις ἔχει, μίαν μὲν ἐκ τοῦ Θεοῦ καὶ Πατρὸς, ἥτις καὶ πρώτη γέννησις λέγεται· καὶ ἕτεραν ἐκ τῆς σαρκὸς, ἥτις καὶ δευτέρα γέννησις λέγεται. Καὶ ὡσπερ ὁ λόγος ἡμῶν, κἄν γεννηθῆ τὴν πρώτην (25) γέννησιν ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς, ἀλλ' ὅμως ἀφανὴς ἐστί, καὶ οὐ φανεροῦται, ἀλλὰ πάλιν μετὰ τὴν γέννησιν μένει ἐν τοῖς

of man has a double engendering and is generated (lit. born) twice; one time is begotten by the soul, another one by the lips. And the logo of man is begotten by the soul when someone considers saying something. The consideration is said to be the first birth of the logos, because he is considering saying that word; he does not say this logos/word by his lips but the soul keeps the logos/word within (lit. in soul's bosom); and that consideration is the first birth of logos by the soul. But even if the logos/word is given birth by the soul, first birth when the soul considers it but does not reveal it, yet is keeps it. But when [the soul] is willing to reveal the logos/word then gives birth to it from the lips. Then [the soul]

gives birth to [or, generates] the logos/word from the lips. This second birth of the logos from the lips, this reveals the logos to everyone and is not said anymore that the logos is unseen, but it [comes to be] seen. And when the logos is given birth from the lips then everyone hears it and comes to be seen by everyone; and this birth from the lips is called second birth of logos/word; thus, there are two births of our logos/word; the one from the soul when considers saying the logos/word, which is also called first birth; and there is another one from the lips, that reveals the logos/word to every man, which is also called second birth. So, learn accurately that just as the logos of man has two birth, one from the soul and another one from the lips, the same way also the Logos of God has two births, one from the God and Father, which is also called first birth; and another one from the flesh, which is also called second birth. And just as our logos, even if it is given its first birth from the soul, but still remains unseen, and does not reveal itself, but even after the birth remains in the soul's bosom; the same way also the Logos of God, even also was born

ψυχικοῖς κόλποις· οὕτως καὶ ὁ τοῦ Θεοῦ Λόγος, καὶ ἐγεννήθη πρὸ τῶν αἰώνων ἐκ τοῦ Θεοῦ καὶ Πατρὸς, ἀλλ' οὐκ ἐφανεροῦτο τοῖς ἀνθρώποις· (30) παρέμενε δὲ πάλιν ἐν τοῖς κόλποις τοῖς πατρικοῖς. Καὶ ὡσπερ ὁ ἡμέτερος λόγος, ὅταν βουληθῶμεν, γεννᾶται ἐκ τῶν χειλέων ἡμῶν, καὶ φανεροῦται ἐν τοῖς ὅλοις ἡμῶν πλησιάζουσιν· οὕτως καὶ ὁ τοῦ Θεοῦ Λόγος, ὅταν εὐδόκησεν, ἐγεννήθη ἐκ τῶν χειλέων τῶν (35) προφητῶν, καὶ ἐκ τῆς πανάγνου Μαρίας, καὶ τότε γέγονε φανερὸς ἐν ὅλῳ τῷ κόσμῳ. Ὡς γὰρ φανεροῦται ὁ ἡμέτερος λόγος γεννηθεὶς ἐκ τῶν χειλέων ἡμῶν, οὕτως δὴ καὶ ὁ τοῦ Θεοῦ Λόγος, γεννηθεὶς ἐκ τῆς σαρκὸς τῆς ἀειπαρθένου Μαρίας, ἐφανερώθη πάση (40) τῇ κτίσει, καὶ οἱ πιστεύσαντες αὐτῷ σώζονται. Καὶ ὡσπερ ὁ ἡμέτερος λόγος, γεννηθεὶς ἐκ τῶν χειλέων ἡμῶν, ὅταν ἀπ' αὐτῶν τῶν χειλέων γεννᾶται, οὔτε ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς λείπει, οὔτε ἀπὸ τῶν ἰδίων χειλέων, οὔτε ἀπὸ τῶν ὠτῶν τῶν ἀκουόντων, ἀλλ' ἔνι καὶ ἐν (45) τῇ ψυχῇ, καὶ ἐν τοῖς χείλεσιν ἡμῶν, καὶ εἰς τὰ ὄτα τῶν ἀκουόντων, καὶ οὐ λείπει ποθὲν, καὶ χίλια

τῶν ἀκουόντων, καὶ οὐ λείπει ποθὲν, καὶ χίλια καὶ χίλια χιλιάδες ἀκουσῶσι τοῦ λόγου, οὐκ ἐλαττονοῦται ὁ λόγος, ἀλλ' αἰὶ ἡμῶν πληρέστατος ἦν· οὕτως καὶ ὁ τοῦ Θεοῦ Λόγος, καὶ ἐγεννήθη ἐκ τῆς Παρθένου (50) Μαρίας, καὶ ἐκ τῶν χειλέων τῶν προφητῶν, ἀλλ' οὐκ οὔτε ἀπὸ τοῦ Πατρὸς ἔλειπε, οὔτε ἀπὸ τῆς σαρκὸς, οὔτε ἀπὸ πάντων τῶν ἀνθρώπων, οὔτε ἀπὸ ὅλης τῆς κτίσεως, ἀλλὰ πανταχοῦ παρῆν, καὶ οὐκ ἠλαττονήθη, ἀλλὰ πληρέστατος ἦν. Καὶ οὕτως νόει περὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ καὶ Λόγου, ὅτι διπλῆν ἔχει τὴν γέννησιν, μίαν ἐκ τοῦ Θεοῦ καὶ Πατρὸς, καὶ μίαν ἐκ τῆς σαρκὸς· καὶ ἡ μὲν ἐκ τοῦ Πατρὸς προαιώνιος, ἡ δὲ ἐκ τῆς σαρκὸς ἐπ' ἐσχάτων τῶν ἡμερῶν· ὡσπερ καὶ ὁ ἡμέτερος λόγος πρῶτον γεννᾶται ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς, καὶ τότε ἐκ τῶν χειλέων. Καὶ ταῦτα περὶ τῶν δύο γεννήσεων τοῦ Λόγου τοῦ Θεοῦ.

before the ages from the God and Father, but was not revealed to men; he remained in the same manner in the fatherly bosom. And just as our logos, when we are willing so, is born from our lips and is revealed to everyone that is approaching us; the same way also the Logos of God, when he was well pleased, was born from the lips of the prophets and from the all-hallowed Mary and then he came to be seen in all the world. And just as is revealed the logos/word that is born from our lips, the same way ought to be also the Logos of God, who was born from the flesh of the ever-virgin Mary, was revealed to all the creation and everyone that believed in him are being saved. And just as our logos/word, having been born from our lips, when is born from these lips, neither is missing from the soul nor from the lips themselves or from the ears of those who are hearing, but it is both in the soul and in our lips and in the ears of those who are hearing and it is not missing from anywhere even if one thousand people

are hearing, and it is not missing from anywhere even if one million people are hearing the logos, and the logos is not diminishing but always was been the most perfect (or, complete); the same way the Logos of God, even he was also born from Virgin Mary and from the lips of the prophets, but actually he was missing neither from his Father, nor from the flesh, or from all the people, or from all the creation but he was present everywhere, and he was not diminished but he was more perfect (or, completed). And you should think about God and Logos this way, that he has a double birth, one from the God and Father and one from the flesh; and the one from God is from before the ages (or, eternal), and the other one from the flesh in the last part of the days; just as our logos/word is born by the soul and then

Ἐρώτ. ε'. Τί τὸ κοινὸν τῆς ἁγίας Τριάδος; **Ἀπόκ.** Κοινὸν ἢ οὐσία· κοινὸν τὸ ἄναρχον· κοινὸν ἢ δύναμις, ἢ ἀγαθότης, ἢ σοφία, ἢ δικαιοσύνη. Πάντα γὰρ ἐξ ἴσου ἔχει ὁ Πατήρ, καὶ ὁ Υἱὸς, καὶ τὸ ἅγιον (5) Πνεῦμα, πλὴν τῶν ἰδίων αὐτῶν. Ἴδιον γὰρ τοῦ μὲν Πατρὸς τὸ ἀγέννητον, τοῦ δὲ Υἱοῦ τὸ γεννητὸν, τοῦ δὲ ἁγίου Πνεύματος τὸ ἐκπορευτὸν.

Ἐρώτ. ζ'. Ἐπὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ πόσας οὐσίας ὁμολογεῖς; **Ἀπόκ.** Μίαν οὐσίαν λέγω, μίαν φύσιν, μίαν μορφήν, ἓν γένος, μίαν δόξαν, μίαν ἀξίαν καὶ κυριότητα.

Ἐρώτ. ζ'. Ὑποστάσεις δὲ πόσας ὁμολογεῖς ἐπὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ; **Ἀπόκ.** Τρεῖς ὑποστάσεις ὁμολογῶ, τρία πρόσωπα, τρία ἴδια, τρία ἄτομα, καὶ τρεῖς χαρακτῆρας.

Ἐρώτ. η'. Διὰ τί λέγεται ὁ Πατήρ Πατήρ; **Ἀπόκ.** Πατήρ λέγεται ὁ Θεὸς, ὡς τὰ πάντα τηρῶν· ὡσαυτεῖ πάντων τηρητής.

Ἐρώτ. θ'. Καὶ ὁ Υἱὸς διὰ τί λέγεται Υἱός; (23) **Ἀπόκ.** Υἱὸς λέγεται παρὰ τὸ οἶος, ἢ γουν ὁποῖος καὶ ὁμοῖος· οἶος γὰρ ὁ Πατήρ, τοιοῦτος καὶ ὁ Υἱὸς, καὶ τροπῇ τοῦ ο εἰς υ, υἱός. Ὁμοῖος γὰρ ὁ Υἱὸς τῷ Πατρί.

Ἐρώτ. ι'. Καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα διὰ τί λέγεται Πνεῦμα; **Ἀπόκ.** Πνεῦμα λέγεται παρὰ τὸ πᾶν νεῦμα ὀξεῶς ἐπινοεῖν, ἢ γουν πᾶσα νεῦσις συντόμως ἐπινοεῖται δι' αὐτοῦ.

from the lips as well. And all these are about the two births of the Logos of God.

Question 5: What is common [thing] for the holy Trinity?

Answer: Common [thing] is the essence; common is the eternity (lit. beginninglessness); common is might, kindness, wisdom, justice. All of them equally belong to the Father, to the Son and to the holy Spirit, except their peculiar characteristics. Peculiar to the Father is unbegottenness [or, ungeneratedness], to the Son is begottenness [or, generatedness], and to the holy Spirit is procession.

Question 6: About God, how many essences do you confess?

Answer: I declare one essence, one nature, one form, one race [of beings], one glory, one [moral] value and lordship.

Question 7: How many substances do you confess about God?

Answer: Three substances I confess, three persons, three peculiar characteristics, three persons and three characters.

Question 8: Why the Father is called “Father”?

Answer: The God is called “Father” (→«Πα»-«τηρ») as he is taking care of all things; as if he was the keeper of all things.

Question 9: And why the Son is called “Son”?

Answer: He is called “Son” («υἱός») from «οἶος», that is “of what sort” and “similar”; that means of what sort is the Father such is also the Son, and by a change of the letter ο to υ, becomes «υἱός» (Son). For the Son is similar to the Father.

Question 10: And why the Spirit is called “Spirit”?

Answer: It is called “Spirit” (→«π»-«νεῦμα») from «πᾶν νεῦμα ὀξεῶς ἐπινοεῖν» (“contriving sharply every decision [or cause, lit. nod]”), that is, every decision [lit. nod] is swiftly contrived through it.

«Τὸ γὰρ ἅγιον Πνεῦμα τὰ πάντα ἐρευνᾷ καὶ τὰ βάθη τοῦ Θεοῦ».

Ἑρώτ. ια'. Ἐπὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ πόσα αἷτια; **Ἀπόκ.**

Ἐν αἷτιον ἐπὶ Θεοῦ λέγω, καὶ τοῦτό ἐστιν ὁ Πατήρ. Αὐτὸς γὰρ ὁ Πατήρ γεννᾷ τὸν Υἱόν, καὶ ἐκπορεύει καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα. Λοιπὸν γίνωσκε, ὅτι ὁ Πατήρ μόνος ἐστὶν αἷτιος· ὁ δὲ Υἱὸς οὐκ ἔστιν αἷτιος, ἀλλ' αἷτιατός. Ὡστε μὲν αἷτιός ἐστι μόνος ὁ Πατήρ· τὰ δὲ αἷτιατὰ δύο, ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα. Αἷτιος δὲ λέγεται ὁ Πατήρ, διότι γεννᾷ, καὶ οὐ γεννᾶται, ἐκπορεύει καὶ οὐκ ἐκπορεύεται. Γεννᾷ μὲν τὸν Υἱόν· ἐκπορεύει δὲ καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον. Καὶ διὰ τοῦτο λέγεται ὁ Πατήρ αἷτιος.

Ἑρώτ. ιβ'. Καὶ πόσα αἷτιατά; **Ἀπόκ.**

Αἷτιατὰ δύο, ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα. Οὐ γεννᾷ ὁ Υἱὸς, ἀλλὰ γεννᾶται, καὶ διὰ τοῦτο λέγεται αἷτιατός. Λοιπὸν ἐάν τις ἐρωτήσῃ, ὅτι ἐπὶ Θεοῦ πόσα αἷτια ὁμολογεῖς; εἰπέ, ἐν αἷτιον λέγω. Καὶ ποῖόν ἐστι τοῦτο; Ὁ Πατήρ. Καὶ διὰ τί λέγεται αἷτιος ὁ Πατήρ; Διότι γεννᾷ τὸν Υἱόν καὶ ἐκπορεύει καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα. Ἐάν δὲ ἐρωτήσῃ σε, ὅτι πόσα αἷτιατὰ λέγεις ἐπὶ τοῦ Θεοῦ; εἰπέ δύο. Ποῖα δὲ ταῦτα; Ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα. Καὶ διὰ τί λέγονται αἷτιατά; Διότι γεννᾶται ὁ Υἱὸς, καὶ οὐ γεννᾷ· ἐκπορεύεται δὲ καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα, καὶ οὐκ ἐκπορεύει.

Ἑρώτ. ιγ'. Ἐπὶ τῆς ἁγίας Τριάδος τίς

πρῶτος; **Ἀπόκ.** Ἐπὶ τῆς ἁγίας Τριάδος οὐδεὶς πρῶτος, (5) καὶ οὐδεὶς ὕστερος, ἀλλ' ἅμα Πατήρ, ἅμα Υἱὸς, ἅμα Πνεῦμα ἅγιον· καὶ διὰ τοῦτο καὶ συνάναρχοι λέγονται, καὶ ἄναρχοι. Ἄναρχον δὲ λέγεται τὸ πρὸ τῆς ἀρχῆς ὄν. Ἄναρχος λοιπὸν ὁ Πατήρ, ἄναρχος ὁ Υἱὸς, ἄναρχον τὸ Πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον. Καὶ οὐχ ὁ μὲν πρῶτος, (10) ὁ δ' ὕστερος, ἀλλ' ἅμα οἱ τρεῖς, Πατήρ, Υἱὸς καὶ Πνεῦμα ἅγιον. Διὰ τοῦτο καὶ συνάναρχοι καὶ εἰσὶ καὶ ὀνομάζονται.

Ἑρώτ. ιδ'. Σαφήνισον ἡμῖν καὶ τοῦτο, πῶς ὁ Υἱὸς (15) καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ γεννᾶται ἐκ Πατρός· τοῦτο γὰρ ἐκπλήττει ἡμᾶς. **Ἀπόκ.**

Ἐπεὶ ὁ Θεὸς ἀθεώρητός ἐστι καὶ

“For the Spirit searches everything, even the depths of God.” [1Co 2:10]

Question 11: About God, how many causes [lit. it-causes]?

Answer: I speak about one cause regarding God, and this is the Father. The Father himself gives birth to [or, generates] the Son, and proceeds also the Spirit. Thus, get to know that only the Father is cause [lit. he-cause]; but the Son is not cause but the effect [or, the product of the cause]. Therefore, there is only one cause the Father, but there are two effects: the Son and the Spirit. Cause is called the Father because he generates and he is not generated, he proceeds but he is not proceeded. He generates the Son; but he proceeds the holy Spirit. And this is the reason the Father is called cause.

Question 12: How many effects [lit. it-effects]?

Answer: The effects are two: the Son and the Spirit. The Son does not generate but he is generated, and this is the reason that he is called effect [lit. he-effect]. Then, if someone asks how many causes about God you are confessing, answer him: I speak about one cause [lit. he-cause]. And which is that? The Father. And why the Father is called cause? Because he generated the Son and proceeds also the Spirit. And if he asks you how many effects [lit. it-effects] about God, tell two. And which are they? The Son and the Spirit. And why they are called effects? Because the Son is generated, and he does not generate; the Spirit is also proceeded, and it does not proceed.

Question 13: About the holy Trinity, who is the first one?

Answer: About the holy Trinity no one is first, and no one is subsequent, but at the same time the Father, at the same time the Son, at the same time the holy Spirit; this is the reason that they are called coeternal (lit. cobeginningless). Eternal (lit.

ἀνερμήνευτος, οὐδὲ τοῦτο ἐρμηνεύσαι
δυνάμεθα.

Πῶς γὰρ τις ἐρμηνεύσαι δύναται, ὃ οὐδέπω
αὐτὸς ἐθεάσατο, (20) ἢ παρ' ἄλλων ἀκήκοε
πώποτε; Πλὴν ἐκ τῶν ποιημάτων αὐτοῦ,
φημί, τοῦ Λόγου καὶ Θεοῦ τυπικῶς
εἶπωμεν, ὅσον τὸ κατὰ δύναμιν. Νοητέον
μὲν, ὅτι, ὡσπερ ὁ λόγος τοῦ ἀνθρώπου
γεννᾶται ἀπὸ τῆς ψυχῆς ἀσπόρως καὶ
ἀκατανοήτως, οὕτως γεννᾶται καὶ ὁ (25)
Λόγος ἀπὸ τοῦ Πατρὸς. Καὶ ὡς γεννᾶται
πῦρ ἐκ τοῦ πυρός, καὶ φῶς ἐκ τοῦ φωτός,
οὕτως γεννᾶται ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ
ἀπὸ τοῦ Πατρὸς.

Ἑρώτ. ιε'. Καὶ τὸ ἅγιον Πνεῦμα πῶς
ἐκπορεύεται ἀπὸ τοῦ Πατρὸς; (30) **Ἀπόκ.**
Πρέπει σε καὶ περὶ τούτου μὴ ἐρωτᾶν. Καὶ
τοῦτο γὰρ ἀνερμήνευτον. Πλὴν μάθανε
καὶ περὶ τούτου. Ὡσπερ οὖν ἡ ἀναπνοὴ τοῦ
ἀνθρώπου ἐκ τῆς ψυχῆς ἐκπορεύεται,
οὕτως καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα τὸ ἅγιον παρὰ τοῦ
Πατρὸς ἐκπορεύεται. Καὶ ὡς ἡ Εὐα οὔτε
(35) γεννητὴ οὔτε ἀγέννητος, ἀλλὰ μέσως,
οὕτως καὶ τὸ ἅγιον Πνεῦμα παρὰ τοῦ
Πατρὸς ἐκπορεύεται. Καὶ γὰρ ὁ Ἄδὰμ
ἀγέννητος, ὁ δὲ Σῆθ γεννητὸς, καὶ ἡ Εὐα
ἐκπορευτὴ. Ἡ γὰρ Εὐα οὔτε ἐγεννήθη, ὡς
ἐγεννήθη ὁ Σῆθ, οὔτε ἀγέννητος ἦν, ὡσπερ
ὁ Ἄδὰμ. (40) ἀλλ' ἐπορεύθη ἐκ τῆς
πλευρᾶς τοῦ Ἄδὰμ. Καὶ ἦν ὁ Ἄδὰμ
ἀγέννητος εἰς τύπον τοῦ ἀγεννήτου
Πατρὸς· ὁ δὲ Σῆθ γεννητὸς εἰς τύπον τοῦ

beginningless) is called what is being before
the beginning. Eternal, thus, is the Father,
eternal the Son, eternal the holy Spirit. And
not the former is first, and the latter is
subsequent, but at the same time [all] three,
Father, Son and holy Spirit. This is the
reason that they are, and they are called
coeternal.

Question 14: Make clear to us this as well,
how the Son and Word (lit. Logos) of God
is generated by the Father; we are
astonished at this.

Answer: Since God is invisible and
inexplicable, we are unable to explain this
as well.

How can someone explain, that thing he
has not [yet] seen, or ever heard by others?
Except by the things he made, I assure, we
can typically speak about the Word and
about God, inasmuch as we can. It is for
sure conceivable that, the way that the
human word is generated by the soul
seedlessly and incomprehensibly, the same
way the Word is generated by the Father.
The way the fire is generated by fire, the
same way the Son and Word of God is
generated by the Father.

Question 15: And how the holy Spirit is
proceeding by the Father?

Answer: It is fitting for you not to ask about
that as well. This is also inexplicable. But
learn about that as well. The way the human
breathing is proceeding from the soul, the
same way the holy Spirit is proceeding from
the Father. And the way Eve neither
generated nor ingenerated but in an
intermediate way, the same way the holy
Spirit is proceeding from the Father. And
Adam was ingenerated, but Seth was
generated, and Eve was proceeded. And
Eve neither was born, as Seth was born, nor
she was ingenerated, as was Adam; but she
was proceeded [lit. made her way] from
Adam's rib [or, side]. And Adam was
ingenerated serving as type of the

γεννητοῦ Υἱοῦ· καὶ ἡ Εὐὰ ἐκπορευτὴ ἐκ τῆς πλευρᾶς τοῦ Ἀδάμ εἰς τύπον τοῦ παναγίου Πνεύματος. Εἰς γὰρ τοὺς προ- (45) πάτορας ἡμῶν ἐτυπώθη ἡ ἅγια Τριάς. Ἄλλ' ὁ μὲν Ἀδάμ, καὶ ὁ Σῆθ, καὶ ἡ Εὐὰ σώματα ἦσαν, καὶ χωριστοὶ ἦσαν ἀπ' ἀλλήλων· ὁ δὲ Θεὸς καὶ Πατὴρ, ὁ Υἱὸς, καὶ τὸ ἅγιον πνεῦμα, οὔτε σώματά εἰσιν, οὔτε χωριστοὶ εἰσιν ἀπ' ἀλλήλων. Μόνος δὲ ὁ τύπος τῆς (50) ἀγεννησίας τοῦ Πατρὸς θεωρεῖται εἰς τὸν ἀγέννητον Ἀδάμ, καὶ ὁ τύπος τῆς γεννήσεως τοῦ Υἱοῦ εἰς τὸν γεννητὸν Σῆθ, καὶ ὁ τύπος τῆς ἐκπορεύσεως τοῦ ἁγίου Πνεύματος θεωρεῖται εἰς τὴν ἐκπορευτὴν Εὐάν. Καὶ οὕτως νόει καὶ περὶ τούτου.

Ἑρώτησις ιζ'. Ἄρα χωρεῖται ὁ Θεὸς ἐν ἐνὶ τόπῳ, ἢ οὐ; (55) **Ἀπόκ.** Πρόσθεσ τὸν νοῦν σου, καὶ νόησον, ὅτι ὁ Θεὸς φῶς ἐστὶν ἀθεώρητον καὶ ἀχώρητον· οὔτε θεωρεῖται ὁ Θεὸς, οὔτε χωρεῖται πού. Καὶ ἐπεὶ οὐ χωρεῖται εἰς τὸ πᾶν, πῶς ἐνὶ δυνατὸν φανῆναι ἢ νοηθῆναί τισιν;

Οὔτινος οὐδὲ Μωσῆς ὁ θεόπτης, οὐδὲ οἱ μαθηταὶ τοῦ Λόγου αὐτοῦ ἐν τῷ τῆς μεταμορφώσεως ἐκείνου ὄρει, οὐκ ἄλλος τίς ποτε ἠδυνήθη γυμνήν τὴν θεότητα θεωρῆσαι· ὥστε δηλόν, ὅτι οὐκ ἐν ἐνὶ τόπῳ χωρεῖται, ἀλλὰ πανταχοῦ πάρεστιν (5) ὁ Θεός. Καὶ ταῦτα μὲν περὶ θεολογίας· ἀπάρτι δὲ ἀρξόμεθα λέξαι καὶ περὶ τῆς οἰκονομίας, ἣτοι περὶ τῆς σαρκώσεως τοῦ Υἱοῦ καὶ Λόγου τοῦ Θεοῦ.

Ἑρώτ. ιζ'. Ἴδου ἐρώτημά σοι ἐρωτῶ, σὺ δέ μοι ἀποκρίθητι. Ἐδίδαξας ἡμῖν περὶ τῆς ἁγίας Τριάδος, (10) ὅτι ὁ Θεὸς τρισυπόστατος ἐνὶ, καὶ ὅτι Πατὴρ, Υἱὸς, καὶ Πνεῦμα ἅγιον. Νῦν δὲ ἐρωτῶ σε· Οὗτος ὁ Χριστὸς τίς ἐστι; Περὶ τούτου θέλω μαθεῖν. **Ἀπόκ.** Πάντως ἤκουσας περὶ τῆς ἁγίας Τριάδος, (15) ὅτι ἐν πρόσωπον καλεῖται Πατὴρ, τὸ δὲ ἕτερον Υἱὸς, καὶ τὸ ἄλλο πρόσωπον λέγεται Πνεῦμα ἅγιον.

ingenerated Father; and Seth generated as type of the generated Son; and Eve was proceeded from Adam's rib as type of the all-holy Spirit. In our forefathers was typified the holy Trinity. But Adam, Seth and Eve were [fleshly] bodies, and they were separate from each other; but the God and Father, the Son and the holy Spirit are neither bodies nor are separate from each other. The only type [or, figure] of Father's ingenerateness can be seen in the ingenerated Adam, and the type of Son's generation in the generated Seth, and the type of the holy Spirit's proceeding is seen in the proceeded Eve. Thus, this was you should think about it.

Question 16: Thus, can God be contained in any place or not?

Answer: Put in your mind and understand that God is light inobservable and uncontainable; neither God can be observed, nor he can be contained anywhere. And because he cannot be contained anywhere, how is it possible to become known or comprehended by anyone?

Whom neither Moses who saw God, nor the disciples of his Word on the mountain of his transformation, nor anyone else was able to observe bare the deity; so that it becomes obvious that he cannot be contained in one place, but that God is present everywhere. And these are about theology; right now, we will start describing also about the [divine] economy, that is about the incarnation of the Son and Word of God.

Question 17: Now I will ask you a question and you answer me. You taught us about the holy Trinity, that God is trihypostatic, and that is Father, Son and holy Spirit. Now I'm asking you: This Christ who is he? I want to learn about him.

Answer: You certainly heard about the holy Trinity, that one person is called Father, the other one Son, and the other person is called holy Spirit. So, now, get to know that

Ἴδου λοιπὸν γίνωσκε, ὅτι οὗτος ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ καὶ Πατὴρ ἐνεδύθη σάρκα ἀνθρώπου, καὶ περιεπάτησεν ὡς ἄνθρωπος ἐν τῇ γῆ. ὠνομάσθη οὖν Χριστός, διότι ἐχρίσθη, ἥτοι ἐφόρεσε τὴν σάρκα τοῦ ἀνθρώπου. Καὶ διὰ τοῦτο λέγεται σεσαρκωμένος Θεός, καὶ Χριστός ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ καὶ Θεός, διότι ἐφόρεσε τὴν τοῦ ἀνθρώπου μορφήν.

Ἐρώτ. ιη'. Καὶ τίνα λόγον, ἢ τίνα χρείαν εἶχεν ὁ (25) Θεός, ἡγουν ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ, ἵνα σαρκωθῆ, καὶ ὡς ἄνθρωπος περιπατεῖν ἐν τῇ γῆ; **Ἀπόκ.** Θεὸς οὐδεμίαν χρείαν εἶχε τοῦ σαρκωθῆναι, (29) ἀλλ' ἡ ἀνθρωπότης ἐδέετο ἰατρείας. Ἐπειδὴ γὰρ (30) ἐποίησεν ὁ Θεὸς τὸν οὐρανὸν καὶ τὴν γῆν, καὶ πάντα τὰ ἐν αὐτοῖς, ἔπλασε δὲ καὶ τὸν ἄνθρωπον, καὶ ἔθηκεν αὐτὸν ἐν μέσῳ τοῦ παραδείσου, καὶ ἔταξεν αὐτὸν βασιλέα εἰς πάντα τὰ κτίσματα, ἵνα πάντα δουλεύωσιν αὐτῷ, καὶ κατοικεῖν αὐτὸν ἐν τῷ παρα- (35) δεῖσῳ, ὡς Θεοῦ εἰκὼν. Εἰδὼς τοῦτο ὁ διάβολος, καὶ φθονήσας τὴν τοῦ ἀνθρώπου ἀξίαν, συνεβούλευσεν αὐτῷ τῷ ἀνθρώπῳ παρακοῦσαι τοῦ Θεοῦ, ἵνα διὰ τῆς παρακοῆς ἐξώσῃ αὐτὸν τοῦ παραδείσου καὶ τῆς τοῦ Θεοῦ ἀξίας, καὶ θνητὸν τὸν ἀθάνατον ἀπεργά- (40) σῆται. Ὁ δὲ ἄνθρωπος, ὡς μὴ ἔχων πείραν κακίας τοῦ πονηροῦ,

ἤκουσε τῆς συμβουλῆς τοῦ διαβόλου, καὶ παρήκουσε τοῦ Θεοῦ, καὶ ἔκτοτε ἐδέξατο τὸν θάνατον τῆς ἁμαρτίας, ὁμοίως καὶ πάντες οἱ ἐξ ἐκείνου γενόμενοι ἄνθρωποι, ὡς ἐκ προγόνων τὴν (45) ἁμαρτίαν λαβόντες, ἐκράτησαν ταύτην· καὶ ἴσχυσεν ἡ ἁμαρτία κατὰ τῶν ἀνθρώπων. Ἐπεμψε δὲ ὁ Θεὸς προφήτας καὶ διδασκάλους εἰς τὸν κόσμον· ἵνα διδάξωσι τὸν κόσμον, ἡγουν τοὺς ἀνθρώπους, καὶ στραφῶσιν ἀπὸ τῆς ἁμαρτίας· καὶ οὐκ ἠδυνήθησαν οἱ (50) προφῆται τοῦ διορθώσασθαι. Διὰ τοῦτο εἶπεν ὁ Θεὸς ἐν ἑαυτῷ· Καταβήσομαι, καὶ φορέσω σάρκα, καὶ γενήσομαι ἀνθρωπόμορφος, καὶ διδάξω τὸ πλάσμα μου, καὶ στραφήσεται ἀπὸ τῆς τοῦ

this Son-and-Word of God-and-Father clothed human flesh and walked like human on earth. He was named “Christ” [i.e. “Anointed”] because he was anointed, namely, he wore the human flesh. That’s why he is called incarnated God, and Christ the Son and Word of God and God, because he wore the human form.

Question 18: And what reason or what need did God have so that the Son and Word of God to become incarnated, and to walk on earth as a human?

Answer: There was need to God of becoming incarnated, but humanity was begging for cure. And because God created the heavens and earth and all the things in them, he created [lit. molded] also the man and put him in the middle of the paradise, and appointed him to be king on every creature, so that all of them to serve him and to dwell in paradise, as image of God. The devil, who had seen this and felt envy, advised this man to disobey God, so that by means of his disobedience to drive him out of paradise and of his divine value, and to make mortal the immortal one. And the man, being inexperienced of the vice of the wicked one,

obeyed devil’s advice, and disobeyed God and since then he received sin’s death and similarly all the people that were born from him, having received the sin from their ancestors, they kept it; and the sin prevailed against men. Then God sent prophets and teachers to the world; so that to teach the world, that is, humans, to turn away from sin; and the prophets weren’t able to correct them. Because of it God said to himself: I will go down and I will wear flesh and I will become human-like [or, human-formed] and I will teach my creature to turn away from devil’s advice and become every man like God not by [lit., according to] nature but by [lit., according to] position. And

διαβόλου συμβουλῆς, καὶ ἔσται πᾶς ἄνθρωπος ὡς Θεὸς οὐ κατὰ φύσιν, (55) ἀλλὰ κατὰ θέσιν. Καὶ τοῦτο βουλευθεὶς ὁ Θεὸς εὐδοκίᾳ τοῦ Πατρὸς, καὶ συνεργείᾳ τοῦ ἁγίου Πνεύματος, @1 (789) συγκατέβη ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ, καὶ εἰσῆλθεν εἰς καθαρὰν κοιλίαν παρθένου γυναικὸς, καὶ προσλαβόμενος σάρκα ἐξ αὐτῆς, ἐνηνθρώπησε· καὶ πάλιν ἐκ τῆς γυναικὸς ἐξελθὼν, καὶ ἐγκαταλείψας αὐτὴν καθαρὰν καὶ ἐσφραγισμένην παρθένον ἀμόλυντον, (5) καθάπερ τὸ πρότερον, περιεπάτησεν ἐν τῷ κόσμῳ μετὰ τῶν ἀνθρώπων, ὡς ἄνθρωπος, καὶ τότε ὠνομάσθη Χριστὸς, διὰ τὸ χρισθῆναί τε καὶ φορέσαι τὴν σάρκα τοῦ ἀνθρώπου. Καὶ οὗτός ἐστιν ὁ Χριστὸς ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ, ὁ σάρκα φορῶν.

Ἐρωτ. ιθ'. Καὶ πῶς ἦν δυνατὸν σάρκα παρθένον (10) γεννησάσθαι, καὶ πάλιν μένειν παρθένον; καὶ τοῦτο θαυμαστὸν ἡμῖν καὶ πάντῳ ἐξαίσιον φαίνεται· δίδαξον ἡμᾶς καὶ περὶ τούτου, δεόμεθα. **Ἀπόκ.** Εἰ καὶ θαυμαστὸν ἡμῖν δοκεῖ τοῦτο, ἀλλ' οὐκ ἀνθρώπου τὸ ἔργον, Θεοῦ δέ· ὅπου γὰρ βούλεται (15) Θεὸς, νικᾶται φύσεως τάξις· καὶ πάλιν· «θαυμαστὸς ὁ Θεός,» καὶ «θαυμαστὰ τὰ ἔργα αὐτοῦ.» Πλὴν ἄκουσον περὶ τῆς γεννησάσης Παρθένου ποικίλα καὶ ἐναργέστατα σύμβολα· μνήσθητι, ὅτι παρθένος ὦν ὁ Ἀδὰμ τὴν Εὐὰν ἐγέννησε· καὶ πάλιν παρθένος (20) διέμεινε, καθάπερ τὸ πρότερον. Καὶ ὡσπερ ὁ Ἀδὰμ παρθένος ἐγέννησε καὶ παρθένος διέμεινε, οὕτω καὶ ἡ Θεοτόκος Μαρία, παρθένος οὔσα, ἔτεκε τὸν Χριστὸν, καὶ πάλιν παρθένος διέμεινε. Ἀλλὰ καὶ ἄλλο πρὸς τοῦτο μυστήριον ἄκουσον.

Ὡσπερ οἶκος περιπεφραγμένος πάντοθεν ἀνατολικὸν ἔχων ὑέλινόν τε καθαρὸν καὶ λεπτότατον παραθυρίδιον, ἀνατείλαντος τοῦ ἡλίου αἱ ἀκτῖνες αὐτοῦ διαπερῶσι τὸν ὑέλινον καὶ εἰσέρχονται πάντα τὸν οἶκον καταφωτίζοντες· καὶ πάλιν παρερχομένου τοῦ ἡλίου καὶ τῶν αὐτοῦ (30) ἀκτῖνων ἐξερχομένων, ὁ ὑέλινος οὐ συντρίβεται, ἀλλ' ἀβλαβῆς ἐκ τῶν εἰσερχομένων τε καὶ

being this the will of God by Father's well-pleasing and with holy Spirit's cooperation, the Son and Word of God agreed (lit., came down [to aid]) and got into a clean womb of a virgin woman, and having received flesh by her, he become incarnated; and again when he came out of the woman, and having left behind the clean and sealed virgin who was undefiled, just as it was before, he walked in the world with the humans, like a human, and then he was called "Christ," for his being anointed and his wearing the human flesh. And this one is Christ the Son and Word of God, he who wears flesh.

Question 19: And how is it possible a virgin to give birth to flesh and still remain virgin? This seems wonderful and wholly remarkable to us; we beg you to teach us about it.

Answer: Even though we consider it wonderful, it isn't a man's work, but God's; and in whatever God is willing, the natural order is overcome; and again: "Admirable is God," and: "Wonderful [or, admirable] are his works." However, listen about various and clear symbols regarding the Virgin who gave birth; remember that Adam was virgin when he begot [lit., gave birth] Eve; and he remained virgin, as he was beforehand. And in the way that the virgin Adam begot and remained virgin, this way also Virgin Mary, while virgin, gave birth to Christ, and all the same she remained virgin. But listen to another mystery related to this.

In the way that a house, shut in on all sides, has towards the east a small window of pure and thin glass, and when the sun is rising its rays are penetrating the glass and they are getting into the whole house and are lighting it up; and again when the sun is leaving and of his rays coming out, the glass does not get broken, but remains unhurt by their impact as they pass in and out, the

ἔξερχομένων προσκρούσεων τοῦ ἡλίου διαμένει ἀκτίνων· οὕτω μοι νόει καὶ περὶ τῆς ἀειπαρθένου Μαρίας. Αὕτη γὰρ ἡ πάναγνος, ὡς οἶκος οὔσα περιπεφραγμένος, ὁ Υἱὸς (35) καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ καθάπερ ἀκτὶς θεϊκὴ ἐκ τοῦ ἡλίου τῆς δικαιοσύνης τοῦ Πατρὸς κατελθὼν, καὶ διὰ τοῦ ὑελίνου παραθυριδίου τῶν ὠτίων αὐτῆς εἰσελθὼν, τὸν πανάγιον οἶκον αὐτῆς κατεφώτισε, καὶ πάλιν ὡς οἶδεν αὐτὸς, ἐξῆλθε, μὴ λυμήνας τὴν παρθενίαν (40) ἐκείνης τὸ σύνολον· ἀλλ' ὡς πρὸ τοῦ τόκου, καὶ ἐν τῷ τόκῳ καὶ μετὰ τὸν τόκον παρθένον ἀγνήν διεφύλαξε. Σὺν τούτοις δὲ καὶ ἕτερον φωτολαμπὲς καὶ θαυμαστότατον, κἀκείνων παρόμοιον ἐκτύπωμα ἄκουσον. Ὁ μαργαρίτης ἐν τῇ Ἐρυθρᾷ θαλάσῃ (45) γίνεται· γίνεται δὲ οὕτως. Αἱ ἄκραι τῆς Ἐρυθρᾶς θαλάσσης ξηραὶ εἰσιν, ὀλίγου χύσιν ὕδατος ἔχουσαι. Εὐρίσκονται δὲ ἐκεῖσε ὄστρακοδέσματά τινα θαλάσσια ἐν πάσῃ τῇ Ἐρυθρᾷ θαλάσῃ ἐκείνῃ, πίνναι ὀνομαζόμενα. Ἰστανται οὖν αἱ πίνναι ἐκεῖναι ἀει κεχηνυῖαι, καὶ ἐκδεχόμεναι βρώματα εἰς τροφήν αὐτῶν. Ἐν γοῦν τῷ ἴστασθαι αὐτὰς κεχηνυίας καὶ ἐκδεχομένας τὴν ἑαυτῶν τροφήν, συχνῶν γενομένων ἐκεῖσε τῶν ἀστραπῶν, κατέρχεται ἡ ἀστραπή πρὸς τὴν πίνναν, καὶ εὐρίσκουσα τὰ τῆς πίννης ὄστρακα @1 (55) (792) ἀνεφγμένα, εἰσέρχεται εἰς αὐτήν· ἡ δὲ πίννα, εὐθύς συστελλομένη καὶ συσφιγγομένη καθ' ἑαυτήν, ἐντὸς αὐτῆς ἀποκλείει τὴν ἀστραπήν. Ἡ δὲ ἀστραπή, τυλισσομένη εἰς τοὺς φορβεῖους τῶν ὀφθαλμῶν τῆς πίννης, καταλαμπρύνει αὐτοὺς, καὶ ποιεῖ αὐτοὺς (5) μαργαρίτας. Ἐξερχόμενοι δὲ οἱ μαργαρίται ἀπὸ τῆς πίννης, πίπτουσι πρὸς τὸν αἰγιαλὸν τῆς θαλάσσης ἐκείνης, καὶ οὕτως εὐρίσκουσιν αὐτοὺς οἱ γυρεύοντες αὐτούς. Οὕτως μοι νόει καὶ περὶ τῆς σαρκώσεως τοῦ Λόγου.

Θάλασσα μὲν ὁ κόσμος, καὶ ἡ Παρθένος (10) κογχύλη. Ἰστατο δὲ ἡ Παρθένος καθάπερ πίννα ἐν τῷ ναῷ, ἐκδεχομένη τὸν

same way you should understand about the ever-virgin Mary. She herself wholly pure [or, chaste], like a house shut up all round, the Son and Word of God like a divine ray descended from the Sun of Justice, the Father, and entered in through the small glass window of her ears, and lighted up her most holy house [or, abode], and again as he knows, he went out without her virginity having been in the least impaired; but as before the birth, so during the birth and after the birth he preserved her pure [or, chaste] virgin. In addition to them there is another light shining and very much admirable, listen to a similar figure [or, pattern] of these [i.e., the previously mentioned]. The pearls are made in the Red Sea; it is made this way. The edges of the Red Sea are dry, there is little water streaming. There are found some sea shellfishes in all that Red Sea, that are called pinnas. These pinnas are standing always with their mouth open and waiting for edible things to eat them. And while they are standing with their mouth open and waiting for their food, there are frequently happening lightnings, the lightning is coming down to the pinna and as it finds its shells open, it gets into it; and the pinna, as it is immediately shrinking and binding tight to itself, within itself is shutting the lightning. And the lightning winding to the pupils of the pinna's eyes, it is brightening them and making them pearls. And when the pearls come out of the pinna, they fall to that seashore, and this way they found them the ones that are looking for them. This way you should also understand about the incarnation of the Word.

The sea is [or, means] the world, and the Virgin is the murex. The Virgin was standing—like the pinna—in the temple,

οὐράνιον ἄρτον Χριστὸν τὸν Θεὸν, ὃς καὶ κατελθὼν καὶ εἰσελθὼν ἐν αὐτῇ, ὡς ἀστραπὴ, καὶ ἐντετυλιχθεὶς ἐν ταῖς λαγόσι τῆς παρθενίας αὐτῆς, λαμπροειδῆ κατεσκεύασε τὴν παναγίαν σάρκα, ἣν προσελάβετο σαρκωθείς· καὶ οὕτως ἐγεννήθη ἐξ αὐτῆς ὡς καθαρὸς καὶ πολυτίμητος μαργαρίτης ὁ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ χωρὶς ἄρρενος συνουσιασμοῦ. Καὶ ὡς περὶ ὁ μαργαρίτης οὐράνιος ἐστὶ καὶ ἐπίγειος, οὐράνιος μὲν κατὰ τὴν ἀστραπὴν, (20) ἐπίγειος δὲ κατὰ τὴν συμπλοκὴν τῶν ὀφθαλμῶν τῆς πίννης· οὕτω καὶ ὁ Χριστὸς οὐράνιος ἐστὶ καὶ ἐπίγειος· οὐράνιος μὲν κατὰ τὴν θεότητα, ἐπίγειος δὲ κατὰ ἀνθρωπότητα. Καὶ ὡς περὶ ὁ μαργαρίτης κατασκευάζεται ἄνευ συνουσίας ἄρρενος καὶ θήλεος ἐξ (25) ἀστραπῆς καὶ τῆς πίννης, οὕτως καὶ ὁ Χριστὸς ἐγεννήθη ἄνευ συνουσιασμοῦ ἄρρενος καὶ θήλεος ἐκ τῆς θεότητος, καὶ τῆς σαρκὸς τῆς Παρθένου. Καὶ ὡς περὶ ὁ μαργαρίτης συντριβόμενος, πολλάκις ἢ μὲν ὕλη τῶν ὀφθαλμῶν τῆς πίννης συντριβεται καὶ διαλύεται, οὐχὶ δὲ καὶ ἡ λαμπρότης τῆς ἀστραπῆς πάσχει, ἀλλ' ἢ μὲν λαμπρότης τῆς ἀστραπῆς ἀπαθῆς διαμένει, ἢ δὲ ὕλη τῶν ὀφθαλμῶν τῆς πίννης μόνη συντριβεται καὶ πάσχει· οὕτως καὶ ἐπὶ τοῦ Χριστοῦ δεῖ σε νοεῖν. Μαστιζομένου γὰρ αὐτοῦ τοῦ Σωτῆρος ἡμῶν, καὶ πάσχοντος ὑπὸ τῶν ἀπίστων Ἰουδαίων ἐν τῷ σταυρῷ, ἢ μὲν ὕλη τῆς σαρκὸς, ἢ γουν ἢ ἀνθρωπότης, μόνη ἔπασχε, ἢ δὲ θεότης ἀπαθῆς διέμεινε. Καὶ ταῦτα λέγων, ἀντιστομίζεις Θεοπασχίτας, καὶ τὴν ἔνσαρκον διδάσκεις οἰκονομίαν. Ἐντεῦθεν σοὶ τὸ ἀμφίβολον, ἀγαπητέ, χάριτι Χριστοῦ διαλύεται.

Ἐρώτ. κ'. Ἴδου ταῦτα πάντα, θεοεἰκελε Πάτερ, ἀρμοζόντως ἡμῖν ἐδίδαξας. Ἄξιοῦμέν σε δὲ, ἵνα καὶ τοῦτο ἡμῖν ἐρμηνεύσης τὸ ἀπορούμενον, διὰ τί οὐκ (40) ἐδίδαξεν ἢ θεότης μόνον τὸν ἄνθρωπον, καὶ ἔσωσεν αὐτὸν ἄνευ σαρκός; τί γὰρ ἤθελε τοῦ φορέσαι τὴν σάρκα; **Ἀπόκ.** Καὶ περὶ τούτου καλῶς ἐρωτᾷς· ὅθεν

waiting for the heavenly bread, Christ the God, who both came down and got into her, like a lightning, and when he was wound in the womb of her virginity, he made bright-looking her most holy flesh, which he took over when he incarnated; and this way the Word of God was also brought forth by her as pure and valuable pearl without intercourse with a male. And the way the pearl is both heavenly and earthly, heavenly as regards the lightning and earthly as regards the interweaving of the pinna's eyes; the same way Christ is both heavenly and earthly; heavenly as regards the divinity, earthly as regards the humanity [i.e. the human nature]. And the way the pearl is produced without intercourse of male and female [but] by a lightning and a pinna, the same way Christ was brought forth without intercourse of male and female [but] from the Divinity and the Virgin's flesh. And the way the pearl is smashed, many times the material of pinna's eyes is smashed and dissolved, but the brightness of the lightning is not harmed, but the brightness of the lightning remains unharmed, and only the material of pinna's eyes is smashed and is harmed; the same way as regards Christ you should understand. When our Savior was whipped and he was suffering [or, being harmed] from the faithless Jews on the cross, only the material of the flesh, that is the humanity [i.e. human nature], was suffering, but the divinity remained unharmed. And by saying these, you shut the mouth of the Theopaschists, and you teach also the incarnate [divine] economy. From this point the ambiguity, dear, is dissolved by Christ's grace.

Question 20: Look, all these, god-like Father, you taught us suitably. We think we are worthy that you explain to us the question: Why did not teach the divinity only the man and saved him without the

ἄκουσον καὶ καλῶς τὴν ἀπόκρισιν. Κατ' ἀρχάς, ὅταν (45) ἐποίησεν ὁ Θεὸς τὸν ἄνθρωπον, καὶ ἐπλανήθη ὑπὸ τοῦ διαβόλου ὁ ἄνθρωπος, οὐκ ἐνίκησεν ὁ διάβολος τὴν θεότητα, ἀλλὰ τὴν ἀνθρωπότητα.

Διὸ καὶ ἔπρεπε πάλιν αὐτὴ ἡ νικηθεῖσα ἀνθρωπότης ἵνα καὶ πάλιν αὐτὴ νικήσῃ τὸν ἐχθρὸν αὐτῆς τὸν διάβολον, καὶ (50) πάλιν παραλάβοι τὸν δι' ἐκείνου πρὶν ἀπολέσαντα θεῖον παράδεισον. Εἰ γὰρ γυμνὴ ἡ θεότης προσήρχετο, καὶ ἐνίκα τὸν διάβολον, ἔμελλε καυχῆσθαι ὁ διάβολος, ὅτι οὐ θαυμαστὸν, εἰ καὶ ἐνικήθη ὑπὸ τῆς θεότητος γὰρ προσβαλὼν ἐνικήθη. Καὶ διὰ τοῦτο (55) οὐ κατεδέξατο ὁ Θεὸς, ἵνα γυμνὴ ἡ θεότης αὐτοῦ προσπαλαίσῃ τὸν διάβολον, ἀλλ' ἠβουλήθη, ἵνα ἡ ἀνθρωπότης ἡ νικηθεῖσα ὑπὸ τοῦ διαβόλου, αὕτη @1 (793) καὶ μόνη νικήσῃ τὸν νικήσαντα ταύτην διάβολον. Προγινώσκων οὖν πάλιν ὁ σοφὸς Θεὸς, ὅτι οὐκ ἠδύνατο μόνη ἡ ἀνθρωπότης νικῆσαι χωρὶς τῆς θεότητος, ἐκρύβη ἐν αὐτῇ τῇ σαρκὶ ἡ θεότης, ὅπως ὁ διάβολος, θεωρῶν τὴν σάρκα, καὶ μὴ γινώσκων, ὅτι ἐν αὐτῇ (5) τῇ σαρκὶ ἡ θεότης ἐστὶ κεκρυμμένη, προσέληθαι καὶ προσπαλαίσῃ τῷ Χριστῷ, καὶ οὕτως νικηθῆ ὑπὸ τῆς κεκρυμμένης θεότητος. Ὅπερ καὶ γέγονεν. Ὡσπερ γὰρ ὁ ἀλιεύς, βουλόμενος κυνηγῆσαι ἰχθύν, οὐ γυμνὸν τὸ ἄγκιστρον βάλλει εἰς τὴν θάλασσαν, ἀλλ' ἐνδύει ἕξωθεν σκώληκα δόλω τὸ ἄγκιστρον, καὶ (10) οὕτως ρίπτει αὐτὸ εἰς τὴν θάλασσαν ἐνδεδυμένον τὸν σκώληκα· ὁ δὲ ἰχθύς, θεωρῶν τὸν σκώληκα μόνον, καὶ μὴ γινώσκων, ὅτι σκώληξ μέσον ἐκείνου ἔχει τὸ ἄγκιστρον, ἀλλὰ νομίζων δίχα ἀγκίστρον τὸν σκώληκα εἶναι μονώτατον, πλανώμενος ὑπὸ τοῦ ἀγκίστρον κρατεῖται· οὕτω καὶ ὁ Χριστὸς ἐποίησε. Βουληθεὶς γὰρ κυνηγῆσαι τὸν ἐν τοῖς ἀπείροις ὕδασι τῆς ἀβύσσου

flesh? Which was the reason that he wore the flesh?

Answer: About this as well it is good that you are asking; thus, it is good to hear the response. At the beginning, when God created man, and the man was deceived by the devil, the devil did not prevail against the divinity, but the humanity.

On this account this defeated humanity should [be] again in order to prevail against its enemy the devil and regain the lost divine paradise by means of him. And if the divinity were to come naked and would prevail against the devil, the devil would boast that it was not marvelous even if he were defeated; he was defeated by the divinity's strike. And for this reason, God did not admitted that his naked divinity struggle with the devil, but he was willing that the defeated by the devil humanity, this and only this prevail against the devil that defeated it. God having again foreknowledge that the humanity could not alone by itself to prevail without the divinity, it was hidden the divinity in this flesh, so that the devil, seeing the flesh and without knowing that the divinity was hidden in this flesh, come and struggle with Christ and this way be defeated by the hidden divinity. Which indeed happened. The way that the fisherman, willing to hunt a fish, does not put the hook bare [i.e. without bait] in the sea, but clothes the hook with a worm from without by deception [lit. using a bait], and this way he throws it, that is wearing the worm, to the sea; and the fish, seeing only the worm, and not knowing that inside the worm there is a hook, but thinking that the worm is totally alone without a hook, deceived he is caught by the hook; the same way Christ acted. As he was willing to hunt the poisonous fish that is dwelling in the limitless waters of the abyss, or rather a great dragon the devil, he did not bring forth his divinity to the devil,

ἐμφωλευόμενον ἰοβόλον ἰχθύν, ἢ μᾶλλον μέγαν δράκοντα τὸν διάβολον, οὐ γυμνῇ τῇ θεότητι αὐτοῦ τῷ διαβόλῳ προσέφερε, ἀλλὰ δόλῳ τὸν σκώληκα τὴν παναγίαν αὐτοῦ σάρκα, ἣν ἐκ τῆς Ἀειπαρθένου Μαρίας, τῆς παναγιωτάτης γῆς, δίχα φυρμοῦ ἐνεδύσατο, κατὰ τὸν φάσκοντα θεῖον Δαβίδ· «Ἐγὼ εἰμι σκώληξ καὶ οὐκ ἄνθρωπος,» ἐκάλυψε τὸ ἱερώτατον ἄγκιστρον τὸν κοσμοσωτήριον αὐτοῦ σταυρὸν, ἐν αὐτῷ προσπαγεῖς, καὶ δι' αὐτοῦ λαθεῖν βουληθεῖς τὴν ἑαυτοῦ θεότητα, ὑφ' οὗ πλανηθεῖς καὶ κρατηθεῖς ὁ ἰοβόλος καὶ ὀφιοδήκτης οὗτος ἰχθύς, ὁ μέγας δράκων διάβολος, ὁ τοῦ παραδείσου ἐξώσας καὶ θανατώσας τὸν ἄνθρωπον, νικηθεῖς ἀπώλετο.

Ὡστε ἡ (30) μὲν θεότης εἰς τύπον τοῦ ἀγκίστρον ἐστίν, ἡ δὲ ἀνθρωπότης εἰς τύπον τοῦ σκώληκος. Θεωρήσας οὖν ὁ διάβολος ἔξωθεν τὸ ἀνθρώπινον καὶ μὴ νοήσας τὴν ἐν αὐτῷ ἔσωθεν ἐγκεκρυμμένην θεότητα, ἐπλανήθη, καὶ προσελθὼν τῇ ἀνθρωπότητι, ἐκρατήθη ὑπὸ τοῦ (35) ἀνεικάστου καὶ ἀκατανικήτου ἀγκίστρον τῆς θεότητος· καὶ οὕτως ἐνικήθη ὁ μέγας δράκων διάβολος. Διὰ τοῦτο οὐκ ἦλθεν ὁ Υἱὸς καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ γυμνῇ τῇ αὐτοῦ θεότητι κυνηγῆσαι τὸν διάβολον, ἀλλ' ἐφόρεσε τὴν σάρκα, καὶ οὕτως εἰσῆλθε. Καὶ (40) αὕτη ἐστίν ἡ αἰτία τοῦ γενέσθαι τὴν σάρκωσιν. Καὶ ὡσπερ αὐτὸς ὁ διάβολος, βουληθεῖς ποτε πλανῆσαι τὸν ἄνθρωπον, καὶ τοῦ παραδείσου ἐκβαλεῖν, οὐ προσῆλθε τῇ Εὐὰ γυμνῇ τῇ ἑαυτοῦ διαβολότητι, ἀλλ' ἐφόρεσε σάρκα τὸν ὄφιν, καὶ οὕτως προσῆλθε, (45) καὶ ἐπλάνησεν αὐτήν· ἦδει γὰρ ὁ δόλιος, ὅτι, εἰ προσέλθῃ αὐτῇ γυμνῇ τῇ διαβολότητι αὐτοῦ, οὐκ ἂν αὐτὴν πλανῆσαι δυνησεται· καὶ διὰ τοῦτο ἐνεδύθη ὡσπερ σάρκα τὸν ὄφιν, καὶ διὰ τοῦ σαρκοφόρου ὄφεως τὴν Εὐὰν ἐπλάνησε. Καὶ ὁ μὲν ὄφιν ἐφαίνετο, ὁ δὲ διάβολος οὐκ ἐφαίνετο. Καὶ διὰ τοῦ φαινομένου ὄφεως ἐνήργει ὁ ἀθεώρητος ὄφιν διάβολος. Δύο γὰρ φύσεις ἐν ἐνὶ προσώπῳ ἀπῆγον τότε ἐπὶ

but by deception [lit. as a bait] the worm [that is,] his most holy flesh, which he wore without intermixing by the Ever-virgin Mary, the most holy earth, according to what was said by the divine David: "I am a worm and not a man," he covered the most sacred hook his world-saving cross, that he was affixed to it, and by means of it to keep unnoticed his own divinity, by which after this poisonous and biting-like-a-snake fish was deceived and conquered, the great dragon the devil, the one who expelled from the paradise and killed the man, perished after being defeated.

This way the divinity is a type of the hook, while the humanity is a type of the worm. And the Devil having seen from without what was human and having not understand that inside in it was hidden the divinity, he was deceived, and coming forth to the humanity, he was conquered by the incomparable and invincible hook of the divinity; and this way the great dragon the devil was defeated. For this reason, the Son and Word of God did not come bare [lit. naked] with his divinity to hunt the devil, but he wore the flesh, and this way he entered. And this is the cause that the incarnation took place. And the way the devil himself, willing some time to deceive the man, and to expel him from the paradise, he did not come forth to Eve having bare [lit. naked] his devilness, but he wore flesh to the serpent, and this way he came forth and deceived her; the deceitful knew that, if he were to come having bare his devilness, he couldn't succeed in deceiving her; and for this reason he wore just flesh to the serpent, and by means of the flesh wearing serpent he deceived Eve. And while the serpent was manifest, the devil was not manifest. And by means of the manifest serpent was acting the unmanifest

τῶν προπατόρων τὴν ἔκπτωσιν. Καὶ ὡσπερ τότε διαβολότης καὶ ὄφιότης δύο φύσεις ἐν ἐνὶ προσώπῳ ἠνώθησαν, καὶ ἡ μὲν μία φύσις, ἡ γουὴ ὄφιότης ἐφαίνετο, ἡ δὲ ἕτερα, ἡτοι ἡ διαβολότης, οὐκ ἐφαίνετο, καὶ ἐξέβαλε τὸν ἄνθρωπον ἐκ τοῦ παραδείσου· οὕτως @1 (796) καὶ ἐπὶ τοῦ Χριστοῦ δύο φύσεις εἰς ἓν πρόσωπον θεότης καὶ ἀνθρωπότης ἠνώθησαν· καὶ ἡ μὲν ἀνθρωπότης ἐφαίνετο, ἡ δὲ θεότης οὐκ ἐφαίνετο, καὶ διὰ τῆς φαινομένης ἀνθρωπότητος ἡ θεότης ἐνήργει ἡ ἀθεώρητος, καὶ τὸν ἐκ τοῦ παραδείσου πάλαι ἐξορισθέντα ἄνθρωπον, αἱ καλαὶ δύο φύσεις αὗται, ἡ θεότης φημί καὶ ἀνθρωπότης, εἰς αὐτὸν πάλιν καὶ νῦν ἐνέβαλον. Καὶ αὕτη ἐστὶν ἡ αἰτία, δι' ἧς ὁ Θεὸς ἐσαρκώθη καὶ ἐγένετο ἄνθρωπος· ὅτι αὐτῷ πρέπει δόξα εἰς ἀπεράντους αἰῶνας. Ἀμήν.

serpent the devil. And two natures in one person [lit. face] brought at that time the fall of the forefathers. And the way that at that time two natures, devileness and serpentness, were united in one person, and while the one nature, that is the serpentness, was manifest, the other one, that is the devilness, was not manifest, and expelled the man from the paradise; the same way in Christ as well two natures, divinity and humanity, were united in one person; and while the humanity was manifest, the divinity was not manifest, and by means of the manifest humanity the unmanifest divinity was acting, and the man that once was expelled from the paradise, these two good natures, I mean the divinity and the humanity, they entered him again. And this is the cause, for which God incarnated and became man; that to him is suitable the glory [to be given] to the endless times. Amen.